

**ORGANIZATIONAL MIGRATION IS ONE OF THE MOST RELIABLE,
EFFECTIVE AND TRENDING TOOLS OF REDUCING
UNEMPLOYMENT RATE IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Annonation: The spread of the corona virus infection has caused great damage to the world economy, along with a sharp reduction in the volume of consumption, the derailment of global production chains and trade relations, a decrease in the price of raw materials in the financial markets, and a deterioration of the economic situation. Also, the coronavirus pandemic has weakened the labor market, putting millions of workers and businesses at risk.

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On the other hand, it is natural that the financial difficulties of labor migrants will have a negative impact on the amount of remittances sent by them. According to World Bank estimates, remittances to developing countries fell by an average of 19.9 percent in 2020. This, in turn, did not fail to have an impact on the migrants working in the external labor migration of our country. We all know that our citizens have had a hard time in foreign countries as migrants are jobless and have lost their income. It is these extraordinary emergency situations that point to speeding up the solution of the issues of taking migrants into social protection and expanding the scale of organized migration, thinking about the fate of the unemployed population at the same time.

The need for state support for life, health and other risks insurance of citizens, as well as for labor protection, labor hygiene and improvement of working conditions during temporary labor activities abroad is increasing day by day. The Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its external labor migration agency are actively taking measures

to protect the rights of our compatriots. It is a gratifying fact that the inclusion of enterprises in the list of "**Unreliable employers**" in cooperation with the representative offices of the countries receiving our migrants and the Consulate General of our country alleviates the problems of our compatriots who are wandering without getting wages. However, along with the integration of the world community, migration processes have also become global. As a result, today participants of external migration can be found in almost all regions and countries of the world. Migration processes are based on economic, political, social, environmental and other reasons. The increase in the number of migrants also requires the expansion of the scope of social protection.

In 2013, there were 230 million migrants worldwide, and today there are more than 281 million migrants worldwide. According to UN data, 174.8 million official migrants were registered worldwide in 2000, and their number has increased by 49% compared to 2000. 50% of the world's migrants settled in 10 countries, 67% in 20 countries. 30 percent of migrants are young people under 29 years of age. The United States is the leader in terms of the flow of migrants, with more than 50 million migrants (20% of the world's migrants). As a result of migration, there is a mixture of representatives of different races and nationalities, which shows mutual influence. According to sociological studies of international organizations on migration, 52% of the world's migrants are men and 48% are women. 31% of migrants are in Asia, 30% in Europe, 26% in North and South America, 10% in Africa, 3% in Oceania.

According to economists, one of the main features of modern migration is the effort of migrants to make life opportunities, plans for the future, to find a way to modern systems of social conditions, especially to get accurate information. Most migrant workers work in the informal sector of the economy in temporary and unprotected jobs. In many countries, because this category of people does not follow the national labor laws of that country, there is an increased risk that they will not be able to take advantage of social and economic protection measures in emergency situations such as pandemics.

Every year, the Institute of Labor Market Research conducts sociological research among migrants who leave the country to work. The information obtained on the basis of studies is constantly presented to the Ministry of Labor and the general public in the form of analytical conclusions. Even during the pandemic and subsequent quarantine restrictions, conversations were held with migrants who returned from working abroad, and necessary measures were developed to provide targeted assistance to our compatriots who fell into difficult conditions. In particular, in the context of the crisis related to SOVID-19, in some countries, there was an increase in discrimination, dismissal, deterioration of working conditions and other similar negative situations against labor migrants. The fact that most migrants cannot use the health care system for various reasons will cause the virus to spread more widely and rapidly. Conversely, in the case of using medical services, it worsened their financial situation and made them more likely to fall into the poverty trap. According to the World Health Organization, in the period before the economic crisis, 100 million people a year worldwide reported falling into poverty due to health costs.

Money earned by migrants in abroad allows them to overcome credit constraints and start a business when they return home. Also, immigrants who have invested in human capital have increased opportunities in the domestic labor market. It should be noted that due to the pandemic, the plans of most immigrants have changed. Simply put, they failed to raise the funds they had planned for, and failed to learn the skills they intended.

Research by the Center for Economic Research and Reform found that 5 percent of expatriates who returned home during the pandemic returned because they had built up their savings. In this case, the maximum benefit of the members of the society from the return of the immigrants depends on the institutions that encourage the use of their existing skills and investments in the homeland. In this case, it is very important to create a system that encourages

them to invest and reintegrate in the labor market. A clear example is that when Uzbek labor migrants return home, 24.4% of urban residents and 27.5% of rural residents remain unemployed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Employment status of returnees from migration, %

Table 1. Migrants worked in 2016-2021 information about countries, %

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
<i>Russia</i>	8,9	7,4	7,5	7,4	7,5	7,1
<i>Kazakhstan</i>	1,4	1,9	1,8	1,5	3	2,2
<i>Turkey</i>	2,4	5,8	7,9	7,7	9,2	8,7

<i>South Korea</i>	1 ,1	2 ,2	1 ,8	1 ,8	2 ,9	2 ,3
<i>Other countries</i>	1 ,6	2 ,1	4 ,1	5 ,4	6 ,2	4 ,7

Taking into account the high number of Uzbek citizens working in Russia and Kazakhstan (**Table 1**), these countries show how urgent the issue of introducing an intergovernmental agreement on social security is. As an example, if we take the signing of the agreement on social security between the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the government of the Republic of Korea on May 10, 2005, we can see that it was beneficial in all respects.

As a clear example of our above opinion, 28% of the migrants who took part in the survey said that they want to go to the Republic of Korea. This indicator shows that wages are relatively high in the Republic of Korea and that migrants' confidence in organized migration has increased (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Countries where migrants want to go through organized migration, %

Based on the conclusions and recommendations of the study of "Issues of foreign labor migration", it was considered important to implement the following steps for the development of this area:

- creation of a database that collects information about the acquired qualifications and skills of citizens who have returned to their place of residence (Bangladesh, Sri Lanka and Egypt's experience);

- Creating a special application for sending currency transfers within the Migration.uz platform. If necessary, establish cooperation with SWIFT and other foreign exchange transaction systems for the implementation of remittances through the application on the basis of low interest rates;

- increasing the number of contracts concluded with foreign employers by the agency for foreign labor migration issues, with the active search and wide involvement of the employer state bodies;

- In cooperation with the Republic Press and Information Agency of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the mass media, to promote organized migration by strengthening the legal, advisory and informational, media-video demonstrations of citizens who want to work abroad in the republic in order to ensure official employment;

- Development of measures to apply "amnesty" to citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who have gone to work and business activities in the CIS countries and have fallen into various unfavorable situations (imprisonment, etc.) (introduction to the discussion at the next summit of the heads of state of the CIS);

- it is necessary to implement a program of continuous monitoring of labor migration (including approval of the relevant research program);

- Development of the concept of external labor migration of Uzbekistan; (Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations);

- development of criteria for the appropriate protection of state interests in the regulation of migration processes and introduction of a responsibility mechanism, development and systematic updating of a personalized (personalized) population database for the purpose of socio-economic monitoring of migrants (Ministry of Internal Affairs, State Statistics Committee, Bodies of self-government of citizens);

- such as development of an information system based on modern technologies for accounting of external and internal migrants within the framework of harmonization of statistical data.

In conclusion, we should emphasize that in order to ensure official employment of citizens who want to work abroad, to strengthen legal, advisory-information, media-video demonstrations, to develop criteria for the appropriate protection of state interests in the regulation of migration processes, and to introduce a mechanism of accountability, migrants For the purpose of socio-economic monitoring, the need to develop a personalized (personalized) database of the population and develop an information system based on modern technologies for systematic updating is still considered urgent. Legal protection and continuous support of the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who have left for labor and business activities in foreign migration and have fallen into various unfavorable situations (imprisonment, fraud, etc.) remains a serious task for the government.

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